

**INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SERVICE
QUALITY AND DESTINATION LOYALTY: A STUDY ON SHAAM-E-
SARHAD VILLAGE RESORT, HODKA, GUJARAT, INDIA**

GOLDI PURI¹

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR

INSTITUTE OF HOTEL AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT

MAHARISHI DAYANAND UNIVERSITY

ROHTAK, INDIA

EMAIL: drgoldipuri@gmail.com

KULDEEP SINGH²

DOCTORAL SCHOLAR (UGC-NET/JRF)

INSTITUTE OF HOTEL AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT

MAHARISHI DAYANAND UNIVERSITY

ROHTAK, INDIA

EMAIL: singh911kuldeep@gmail.com

ARNAB GANTAIT^{3*}

DOCTORAL SCHOLAR (UGC-NET)

DEPT. OF TOURISM STUDIES

SCHOOL OF MANAGEMENT

PONDICHERRY CENTRAL UNIVERSITY,

PUDUCHERRY, INDIA

EMAIL: arnab8376@gmail.com

**CORRESPONDENCE: ARNAB GANTAIT, DOCTORAL SCHOLAR, DEPARTMENT OF TOURISM STUDIES,
PONDICHERRY UNIVERSITY, PUDUCHERRY, INDIA, MAIL ID: arnab8376@gmail.com*

Abstract:

The tourism and hospitality industry in a service sector is nothing but consuming services and gaining new experiences. The success or failure of this industry depends on the quality of services available at the destination. At present, tourism has become a booming industry in India and there has been a huge shift in tourists' attitude from the back of the bus, five-star tour to something more interactive and in that connection, the rural tourism plays an important role. But it is unfortunate that most of the time, while promoting such destination we overlook the quality of available services. Therefore, many a time even if any rural destination has great tourism potentials, it fails to grab the tourists' attention. In this paper the researchers have found that there is a connection in between service quality and destination loyalty through tourist's satisfaction at any place, and destination loyalty ensures increasing volume of tourists at a destination that leads towards the sustained tourism. In this paper the researchers have mentioned the 'Shaam-E-Sarhad' Village Resort, situated in Hodka Village in the state of Gujarat, India, as a case study to examine the relationship between tourism service quality and destination loyalty. Both qualitative and quantitative data have been used in this study. Tourists' feedbacks have been taken from the TripAdvisor. Inc. Finally, Content Analysis Method' has been adapted to analyze the data regarding Service Quality, Satisfaction and Destination Loyalty from the tourists' feedbacks to examine their Interrelationship.

Key Words: Service Quality, SERVQUAL Model, Tourist Satisfaction, Revisit Intention, Recommendation, Destination Loyalty.

[1] Introduction

Tourism was first encouraged in India by a composed exertion of Government of India (GoI) with the initiative taken by Sir John Sargent in 1945, though the rise of tourism in this country begun only when the '6th Five Year Plan' (1978-1980) acknowledged this sector as a standout amongst the most critical division adding to the nation's financial advancement. The World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) in its 2008-Global Report ranked India No —1, for its 'long-term travel growth', and in 2013, the 'Incredible India Campaign' won 'World Travel Award' in the category of 'Asia's Leading Destination' – all these success stories actually indicate the growing popularity of this country as a unique travel destination on the world tourism map in recent time. When India is bracing for new tourism endeavours to grab the attention of special interest tourists like many other countries, a paradigm shift in overall tourists' attitude has also been observed worldwide at the same time, when the new age tourists are looking for more experiencing and interactive holiday options. In this backdrop,

the scope of rural tourism in India is gradually increasing as such form of niche tourism exhorts tourists to spend quality time in a nuanced fashion by engaging them in different ethnic, indigenous and aesthetic practices in rural areas (Singh, Gantait, Puri & Swamy; 2016) and therefore, it offers more enriching tourism experience compared to other popular alternative forms of tourism. As we all know that the overall tourism sector is a highly competitive market place, the quality of services offered at a destination can give that particular place a chance to create a competitive differentiation compared to the other popular tourist places by increasing tourist traffic that can ensure a continuous flow of money into the local economy. Therefore, 'service quality in rural tourism destinations' has now become a commonly discussed topic as 'Service Quality' plays a pivotal role for the growth, development and stability of tourism and hospitality sector overall. Not only the visitors, service consumers, and entrepreneurs but also the researchers from social science, especially from tourism and hospitality domain - all agree with each other that 'Service Quality' does not only mean 'production' and 'final services' rather, its success majorly depends on the 'the manner how its final delivery will be processed' as mostly, the 'final satisfaction to the customers' leads towards 'larger sales profits' and 'more frequent visits'.

In most of the studies, so far, the 'level of satisfaction' has been considered as the most important variable in explaining the relationship between 'service quality' and 'destination loyalty' as the researchers opine that 'high quality service' can achieve 'high tourist satisfaction' that eventually builds the 'image of any destination' which ultimately leads to 'revisit intention', though according to Moon et al. (2011) and Demir (2013), the past investigators have not investigated properly the 'worldwide visitors' recognitions' on the 'service quality' and 'travellers' destination loyalty' in developing nation's tourism industry setting. Here in this study, the researchers have taken a very popular rural tourism site in India i.e. Hodka Village, Gujarat, as a case study with special reference to its Shaam-E-Sarhad village resort (run by the local community people), for a deeper understanding of the role of service quality and its relationship with 'destination loyalty' through 'the level of tourists' satisfaction' in a rural India set up.

[2] Statement of the Problem

Fyall & Leask (2007) consider 'Destination' as an important element in the travel and tourism industry. Buhalis (2000) who explains it more elaborately says, 'destination' consists of a combination of tourism products and services that offer the visitors a unique experience. Rajesh (2013) considers that 'tourists' satisfaction' is a significant element for successful marketing of any destination as it brings back tourists to any destination. Moreover, Oppermann (2000); Chen & Tsai (2008) think that satisfied tourists often recommend their visited places to the others and as we all know these recommendations or references ('Word of Mouth') often acts as a catalyst that increases tourists' flow at any destination and consequently, such phenomenon helps the destination and its people to earn more from tourism revenue. Demir (2013) considers 'destination loyalty' as one of the main earnings of 'Services Quality's success in the area of tourism. Chi & Qu (2008); Yoon & Uysal (2005) argue that even though 'destination loyalty' is an important factor but very negligible number of studies have been conducted so far to assess it. Vinh & Long (2013); Yang et al. (2014) criticized that 'destination loyalty' has not been tested properly in the context of a destination yet. Therefore, Riduan et al. (2015); Akroush et al. (2016) suggest that more research should be done for the sake of deeper understanding of the relationship between 'tourism services quality' and the 'destination loyalty' through 'tourist satisfaction'.

[3] Objectives of the Study

Here the study revolves around the three key objectives in the context of Hodka Village, Gujarat, with a special reference to the Shaam-E-Sarhad Village Resort. (1) The first and foremost objective is to examine the relationship between Service Quality and Destination Loyalty through Satisfaction. (2) The second objective is to identify the 'Service Quality' elements, influencing tourists to be loyal towards the place and the services consumed there. (3) The third objective is to highlight the Service-Gaps found from tourists' frequently made complaints against various service issues, those are somehow negatively affecting the 'Tourists' Satisfaction' and the 'Revisit Intention' leading towards the 'Destination Loyalty'.

[4] Review of Literature

[4.1] *The concept of Service Quality*

Parasuraman et al., (1988) defines service quality as a function of the difference between service expected and customers' perceptions of the actual service delivered. The service quality concept originated from the expectancy-disconfirmation paradigm. **Parasuraman, Berry & Zeithaml (1985)** considers it as a key to success of any service based business. According to **Kotler (2003)**, the 'Service Quality' begins with the clients' expectation regarding any specific service and ends with their perception after consumption. As the idea of 'service quality' lacks an overall agreement regarding its meaning and operationalization, the overall concept is still one of the most arguable topics in service marketing studies (**Gupta & Chen, 1995**). **Bitner & Hubbert (1994)** defines it as an overall impression of the relative inferiority and superiority while, **Kasper et al. (1999)**, **McKercher & Prideaux (2011)** think that service quality depends on customers' expectations. **Jraisat & Sawalha (2013)** mention service quality is all about the 'quality control'. As we all know, that service is multi-dimensional and subjective in nature, measuring service quality is not an easy task. Therefore, to measure the service quality in the service sectors, a number of frameworks have been put forth amongst which the most popular and successful research instrument is the SERVQUAL, designed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (**Parasuraman et al., 1985**), where five service quality dimensions have been taken into consideration: (1) assurance, (2) reliability, (3) tangibility, (4) empathy and (5) responsiveness. Apart from that, **Parasuraman et al. (1985)** mentioned ten determinants those influence the service quality and these are tangibles, access, communication, understanding, courtesy, credibility, competence, security, reliability, and responsiveness. Later on, **Johnston et al. (1990)** tells about twelve determinants of service quality i.e. appearance, availability, cleanliness, comfort, communication, competence, courtesy, friendliness, reliability, responsiveness and security. **Johnston & Silvestro (1990)** further adds five determinants such as helpfulness, care, commitment, functionality, and integrity. **Walker (1990)** recommends quality environment, delivery systems and product reliability together with high-quality individual service – personnel attitude, and skills & knowledge to be considered while measuring the service quality. **Fowdar (2007)** also checked Service Quality on the basis of the SERVQUAL model prepared by Parasuraman et al. (1985) where he considers (1) appealing interior and exterior resort décor, attractive lobby of resort, cleanliness, comfort of rooms, spaciousness of rooms, hygienic bathrooms, convenient location of the resort/hotel, neat and professional appearance of staffs, visually appealing brochures, the overall image of the resort etc. as Tangibility, (2) staff performing services at the time promised, well-trained and knowledgeable staffs, food quality, accuracy in staffs' performances, accurate information

about prices etc. as Reliability, (3) friendliness of staff, courteous employees etc. as Assurance (4) willingness of staff to provide help promptly, availability of staff to provide services etc. as Responsiveness and finally (5) under the dimension of Empathy he mentions elements like special attention towards customers, availability of room services, understanding the customer requirements, listening carefully to complaints, comfortable and relaxed welcome feeling, variety or quality of recreational facilities, security and safety, reasonable prices of the products, provision for evening entertainment etc.

[4.2] The concept of Satisfaction

Several academicians affirm that ‘satisfaction’ and ‘service quality’ are two diverse concepts (Taylor & Baker, 1994; Bitner & Hubbert, 1994; Boulding et al., 1993; Parasuraman et al., 1988) though like ‘service quality’, satisfaction also plays a crucial role in the survival and success of any kind of business (Fen & Meillian, 2005), where the focus is mainly to achieve the profit-making goal. Kozak & Rimmington (2000) suggests that tourist satisfaction is crucial for destination marketing as it not only convinces tourists to consume more similar kind of products and motivates them to return to the places visited earlier but also influences their choices while selecting a destination. Noe & Uysal (1997) considers ‘satisfaction’ as a decisive factor to evaluate the performance of destination products and services. The disconfirmation paradigm in ‘Process Theory’ provides the grounding for the vast majority of satisfaction studies that encompasses four constructs of satisfaction and these are: expectations, performances, disconfirmation and finally satisfaction. Disconfirmation arises from the disparity between the prior expectations and the actual performance. The zero disconfirmation shows a product performs ‘as expected’; while positive disconfirmation indicates that the product performs ‘better than expected’; and negative disconfirmation displays the product ‘performs below expectations’; that often generates dissatisfaction (Yi, 1990; Oliver & DeSarbo, 1988). Spark (2002) measures Satisfaction on the basis of 4 items (1) Value for Money, (2) Accessibility (here in this study, we have used this term as ‘Location’), (3) Service, and (4) Environment (both internal and external). Rajesh (2013), Yoon & Uysal (2005) consider tourist satisfaction as an important constituent for the successful destination promotion activities as according to Chen & Tsai (2007) and Oppermann (2000), satisfaction is very vital from the tourists’ point of view; that motivates them to revisit and/or recommend any destination.

[4.3] The concept of Loyalty

The concept of loyalty has been considered as one of the central signs of success of any business (Pine et al., 1995; Bauer et al., 2002) and Faullant et al. (2008) considers ‘word-of-mouth’ as one of the most indispensable types of loyalty as new clients can be fascinated by the suggestions from the others. The notion of tourist’s loyalty is greatly linked with the performance rather than the feelings. According to Oliver (1993), loyalty often drives the consumers towards ‘repurchasing products’. The study on customer loyalty is mostly concentrated on ‘product related loyalty’ but the ‘loyalty to the services’ has been highlighted very few times (Gremler & Brown, 1996). Zabkar et al., (2010) and Kim & Brown (2012) define a destination as “a location of a group of attractions, tourists’ facilities, and services those constitute the tourism product at any destination level.” The research in service quality so far has small comprehension about the visitor’s loyalty on destination level. According to Vinh & Long (2013); Kim et al. (2013), the study on tourism destination loyalty has developed into attracting supremacy of specialist in services marketing literature. “Since destinations facing heavy competition, destination supervisors should find out the reasons why tourists are loyal towards destination

so that they can tackle the main issues which affect tourist retention” (Chen & Gursoy, 2001). The destination’s success strongly depends on a systematic environmental analysis of tourist motivations and on customer satisfaction and loyalty (McKerchera & Prideaux, 2011). It is very unfortunate that though a good number of studies have been performed to check the satisfaction at destination, limited studies have evaluated destination loyalty (Chi & Qu, 2008; Yoon & Uysal, 2005). According to Petrick et al. (2001) and Chi & Qu (2008), ‘Visitors’ Revisit Intentions’ and their ‘Positive Recommendations’ usually reflect their loyalty towards the product or service.

[4.4] The relationship of Service Quality and Destination Loyalty

Improving Service quality is very essential for any contemporary service based business as it has positive impact over tourist satisfaction, cost reduction, profitability and improved customer loyalty. According to Kumar et al. (2008), service quality is directly related with the tourist satisfaction. Chi & Qu (2009) reveals that tourist satisfaction leads to higher consumer loyalty. Kozak & Beaman (2006) states that tourist satisfaction is an important sign of the intention to recommend a destination and the tourists are more likely to revisit any destination if they are satisfied with the available services and when there is a positive WOM (Word of Mouth) recommendation. According to Lee et al. (2007), it is not necessary that higher satisfaction with a destination will always lead to revisit intention because tourist always want some new experiences that leads them to visit new destinations therefore, they confirms that the ‘service quality’ variable is more dominant on the ‘behavioral loyalty’ compared to the another variable ‘satisfaction’. Though it was studied that there is a direct relationship between satisfaction and destination loyalty (Lee et al., 2005; Crompton, 1995), the relationship between ‘service quality’ and ‘destination loyalty’ has not been properly examined so far in the context of a destination. Therefore, the relationship between ‘service quality’ and ‘destination loyalty’ is still not very clear.

[5] Research Methodology

The research is explorative and case study approach has been taken. The paper adopts a desk-based review process which includes both online and offline resources. Various articles in reputed journals were identified through EBSCO, Science Direct, Google Scholar, like online resources to prepare the ‘Literature Review’. Variables like ‘Service Quality’, ‘Satisfaction’, and ‘Loyalty’ were the keywords to extract the lead works. Then the researchers go through the official website of TripAdvisor. Inc (Indian Version) and gathered all the feedbacks (total feedbacks are 165 in number) given by the tourists, who visited Hodka Village and stay there at least one night. TripAdvisor. Inc is an American Travel and Restaurant Website Company that provides travel-related content as well as it has a separate interactive travel forum, where tourists can give feedbacks over their experience at any destination and therefore, it is very popular and regarded as a trusted source in tourism industry to check the overall visitors’ review to rate any place. TripAdvisor. Inc also certifies various accommodation establishments as per the availability and quality of services. Then, the researchers minutely read all these feedbacks given by these tourists belonging from different age group, profession and nationality on various dimensions of Service Quality, Satisfaction and Loyalty. Content Analysis Method has been applied to scrutinize and infer the data acquired from tourists feedbacks. Following this, various reports published in newspapers, travel magazines, travel blogs, websites etc. pertaining to these variables was collected and data was reported logically. Finally, the draft of the paper was prepared and reviewed twice to make it more accurate.

[6] Case Study on Hodka with Special Reference to Shaam-E- Sarhad Village Resort

Hodka, a typical Kutchi village is located at the heart of the Banni grassland in Rann of Kutch in the state of Gujarat, where the travellers are enchanted by the colorful attire of the locals and the traditional assets of the Kutch in form of various architecture and arts, dance and music, textiles and cuisines. This village is well connected by airways (nearest airport Bhuj, 65 Kms away), railways (nearest railway station is Bhuj), and roadways. The name 'Hodka' is derived from a Gujarati word 'Hodi' that means 'Boat' whereas, in Hindi, it means 'Jheel' i.e. a place where portable water can be found. It is believed that this village has been set up by the 'Halepotra' clan who were the cattle herders and came from the Sindh region about 300 years ago in search of pastureland and later on the 'Meghwals' who are the traditional leather craft and embroidery crafts persons, came from further north and settled here. This village comprises of hamlets each of those are unique. The villagers use mud to construct their houses and it keeps the room-interior cool. Moreover, they use dung and natural dyes in the earth tones to decorate their houses that often impress the visitors. The village girls are taught to embroider at a very early stage of their life and gradually they learn the stitching and making skirts, cholis, quilts, door hangings. Tourists can also find here different embroidered items embellished with mirrors, shells, tassels etc. and can visit around the village hiring the local guides known as 'bhomiya's', who can provide them a proper insight of the village. The Village Tourism Committee of Hodka operates a seasonal Village Resort, 'Shaam-E-Sarhad' (Sunset at the Border), an initiative taken by the ETP (Endogenous Tourism Project) and collaboration between the UNDP (United Nations Development Programme) and the MoT (Ministry of Tourism), Government of India, that promotes local culture and craft based eco-tourism for sustainable livelihoods and integrated rural development. The 'Hodka Endogenous Tourism Project' was first implemented by the 'Kutch Mahila Vikas Sangathan' and later on, the 'Hodka Paryatan Samiti' was set up to run this project. Now this committee manages and operates the tourism activities in Hodka. 'Shaam-E-Sarhad' is situated towards the Northern Kutch, where the haunting landscapes of the endless Rann and the bounty of its local handicrafts offer tourists a first-hand experience of true village life. This village resort opens on 1st October and closes on 31st March every year. The warm hospitality from the villagers, their vibrant culture, arts and artifacts are the main reasons behind the continuous growth of tourist traffic in this village that generates good amount of revenue that again goes back to the Committee members. This village got CNBC AWAAZ's prestigious 'Travel Award' for being the 'Best Tourism Income Generating Project' in 2008 and it is a good example of Responsible Tourism initiative, that is creating new job scopes, helping the village-women, unemployed youth and the disadvantaged groups to articulate their skills through capacity building programmes (Economic Benefit); involving the local people in decision making process and promoting local culture (Social Benefit) and finally preserving the available natural resources (Environmental Benefit) those offer the tourists a genuine rural village ambience during their stays. This Village has also got the prestigious 'Pacific Asia Travel Association Gold Award' for being the 'Best Rural Tourism Project' in 2010 under the 'Heritage Category'.

[6.1] Key Tourism USPs of Hodka Village

Tourism Attractions in Hodka Village		
Key Tourism Attractions	Other Tourism Attractions	Developed Tourism Attractions
Craft	Banni Hospitality	Shaam-E-Sarhad Resort
Rann of Kutch	Unique view of clear night sky	Kutch Utsav
	Traditional Way of Life	Pashu Mela

Table 1 - Source: https://www.equitabletourism.org/files/fileDocuments913_uid15.pdf

[6.2] Tourist Influx and Revenue income in Hodka Village in Recent Past

Table 2 is highlighting that the ‘number of tourists’ and ‘tourism revenue’ from Hodka village, both are growing day by day in a significant note.

Year	Revenue (INR) from Shaam - E- Sarhad	Growth of Tourist Inflow
2005-2006	100000	Hodka village venture had only 50 guests in the first year of opening. In 2006, 1378 daytime guests came along with 998 package tourists. 8 % to 10 % increase in the tourists’ arrival to the village sites after the launch of the Rural Tourism Scheme.
2012-2013	4500000	
www.equitabletourism.org/files/fileDocuments913_uid15.pdf		
www.thealternative.in/lifestyle/travel-another-india-visiting-your-roots/?print=print		
www.pib.nic.in/newsite/erelcontent.aspx?relid=32268		

Table 2 – Revenue earned & Growth of Tourism in Hodka Village from 2005/06-2012/13

[6.3] Available Tourism Products / Services at Shaam – E- Sarhad Village Resort

Promised Service				
Accommodations	At the Resort	In the rooms	Food and Drink	Are You Interested for Crafts, Culture?
SUITE BHUNGAS	Open parking	Double beds in all rooms	Only vegetarian food is served.	Hodka Artists Village
ECO-FRIENDLY MUD TENTS	Front Desk (6am to 11pm)	Extra beds (on request)	In the morning, you can choose between an Indian and a Continental breakfast.	Dhordo village
QUADRUPLE FAMILY COTTAGES	Phone service (local phone calls)	Attached toilets with shower	For lunch and dinner we serve a Gujarati and Kutchi buffet, with a range of vegetables (cooked and fresh), pulses, Indian breads, and local sweets. Indian snacks can be	Great Rann of Kutch

			prepared as listed on the menu.	
STANDARD BHUNGA	Wake up call	Map and brochure with information of the area	Bottled mineral water and non-alcoholic soft drinks are available, together with tea, coffee, and buttermilk.	Khavda
	Room service (6am to 11pm)	Fan	Alcohol Restriction – Alcohol is not served at the resort and consumption is forbidden on the resort premises.	Karo Dungar (Black Hill)
	Laundry	Mosquito Repellents in all rooms	Guests are requested to follow the instructions kept in the rooms.	
	Restaurant (7:30am-9:30 / 12pm-3pm / 7:30pm-10:30pm)			

Table 3 - Source: www.hodka.in

[7] Results

[7.1] Demographical Overview of Tourists

Tourists mostly come as couple or with their family and few visits as individual travellers. It reflects that the visitors have firm belief in overall safety and security of this place, where they can spend quality time accompanied by their family members. It has also been observed from the feedbacks that, tourists are coming from different countries all over the world including UK, USA, The Netherlands, Luxembourg, Canada, Italy, Austria, Australia, Brazil, Mexico etc. whereas, the domestic tourists are coming from different Indian cities like Ahmadabad, Kutch Bangalore, Mangalore, Pune, Gurgaon, Delhi, Lucknow etc. It indicates that this village has become a popular rural tourism destination. In addition, most of the tourists have spent one or two nights and there are few tourists those have even spent more than two nights at Shaam-E-Sarhad. It conveys that the city dwellers are prefer this resort to other accommodation establishments located nearby this village as it offers them more interactive, memorable and off-the-beaten-track experience during their trip to Hodka Village.

[7.2] Impressive Service Quality at Shaam –E- Sarhad village Resort in Hodka

Most of the tourists are impressed over the Service Quality at Shaam - E - Sarhad Resort, Hodka	
Accommodation	Pleasure of staying at Bhungas, tents, and family cottages crafted with indigenous resources
	Local home ambience
Room Facility	Free space inside the room
	Attached toilet
	Well decorated room interiors
	Hot water facility
	Rooms are cool from inside
	from 154 reviews over 90% tourists gave satisfactory feedbacks against sleeping quality
	Appealing interiors and exteriors with warm and wonderful Kutch decorations
Resort ambience	Reception, dining, and seating arenas are bright and cheerful
Food quality	Tasty, well prepared & well displayed food
	Healthy tea/ coffee
	Fresh organic milk from the village
Amenities	Cultural activity at night
	Camp fire
	Local performers are being hired to entertain tourists by Kutchi Folk music and dance performances
	Cheerful evening under the starlit sky
Hospitality	Affable staff
	Friendly villagers
	Earnest hospitality
Authenticity	Authenticity of stay and taste is well maintained
Cleanliness	Rooms are clean to be the best possible in such remote and dusty climatic conditions
Price	Affordable price
	tariff is comparatively lower than other options in Rann
Easy Booking facility	The Shaam-e-Sarhad resort has a well-designed and well documented website where, the tariffs are clearly displayed and there are provisions for guest registration, online booking, check availability facilities, site maps, and tourist attractions are also visually displayed in their website.

Table 4: Impressive Service Quality available at Shaam-E-Sarhad Village found from tourists' feedbacks

Table 4 reflects that the status of the overall service quality available at Shaam-E-Sarhad village resort is up to the mark as from tourists feedback it has been found that most of the tourists have expressed their satisfaction on a wide range of service quality elements like accommodation, room facilities, resort ambience, food quality, amenities, hospitality, authenticity of products, overall cleanliness, price, easy booking facility etc.

[7.3] Positive Correlation between Service Quality and Satisfaction

Total 165 visitors who spent 1 or more than one night participated in this rating. They were asked to rate their 'Overall Satisfaction Level' in terms of Service Quality at Hodka Village including their stay at Shaam – E- Sarhad Resort. **Table 5** shows the result.

Tourists' feedback on overall experience in term of Service Quality	No. of Visitors
Excellent	76
Very Good	63
Average	18
Poor	6
Terrible	2
Total feedbacks	165

Table 5 - Tourists' feedback on overall experience in term of Service Quality, Source: TripAdvisor.Inc (3.09.2018)

Out of 165 feedbacks the researchers have found 76 (46.06 %) tourists to rate their overall experience in terms of 'Service Quality' at Sarhad – E-Shaam Resort, Hodka Village, as 'Excellent', while 63 (38.18 %) have rated it as 'Very Good' and 18 (10.90 %) have rated 'Average'. It shows that most of the tourists (more than 94%) are satisfied with the 'Services Quality' in terms of the

availability of tourists' facilities, warm hospitality from the local people and friendly behavior from the resort staffs. Only 6 (3.63%) are dissatisfied with the 'poor' quality of service whereas 2 (1.21%) rated it 'terrible'.

Table 5 (Source: www.tripadvisor.in/Hotel_Review-g2615717-d1169986-r5583866870-Shaam_e_Sarhad_Village_Resort-Hodka_Village_Kutch_District_Gujarat.html) conveys the fact that whenever, a tourist found impressive service quality he/she has expressed that in a satisfactory note while the service gaps make the visitors somehow unsatisfied. Therefore, we can say both 'Service Quality' and 'Tourist Satisfaction' are correlated where 'Service Quality' is found to be 'independent variable' and Satisfaction is the 'dependent variable' and there is a positive correlation in between these two variables.

[7.4] Influence of ‘Service Quality’ over ‘Destination Loyalty’ through ‘Satisfaction’

No of Tourists feedbacks given positive compliment over service quality / Recommended others to visit this place and consume services/ expressed their desire to revisit the place in recent future (satisfied tourists)	145
No of tourists feedbacks gave mixed or negative compliment over service quality (Unsatisfied tourists)	20

Table 6 – No. of Tourists who express their loyalty towards this rural tourism destination

‘Revisit Intention’ and ‘Positive Recommendation’ reflect consumers’ loyalty towards any product or service, offered to them (Petrick et al., 2001; Chi & Qu, 2008). In this context, here, **Table 6** displays that out of 165 tourists’ feedback collected; only in 20 cases the tourists expressed their dissatisfaction through negative or mixed compliments on the quality of services at Shaam –E-Sarhad village resort in Hodka Village, Gujarat. Otherwise, rest of the tourists (145 out of 165, more than 87.87 %) have given positive compliments (express satisfaction) on this rural tourism site and the service quality at Shaam –E-Sarhad village resort while, many of the respondents have even mentioned that they would love to come again to this place (revisit intention) or recommended this place on a high note (positive recommendation). Therefore, **Table 6** shows most of the tourists are loyal towards this place as well as towards the services (tourism products) they consumed here.

[7.5] Interrelationship between Service Quality, Satisfaction and Destination Loyalty

The following Flow Chart (Fig. 1) is showing the interrelationship in between the three variables Service Quality, Satisfaction and Destination Loyalty in the context of Hodka Village. After going through all the feedbacks given by the tourists, at TripAdvisor. Inc, the researchers have prepared this Flow Diagram that shows that, there is a correlation between ‘service quality’ and ‘satisfaction’ while ‘satisfaction’ can be of two types (1) satisfaction towards the positive direction that makes the tourists ‘satisfied’ and (2) satisfaction towards the negative direction that makes the tourists ‘Complaining’ over the service gaps. It also shows that ‘satisfaction towards the positive direction’ often motivates tourists to ‘recommend’ or ‘refer’ any destination to the others; to revisit the place and to consume the same services repeatedly. Such ‘revisit/repurchase intention’ makes them loyal towards the consumption of services at the destination and the ‘word of mouth’ increases the volume of tourist traffic day by day at any destination and ultimately this phenomenon makes the tourism business sustained at that specific tourist spot.

Fig 1 – Relationship between Service Quality, Tourists’ Satisfaction and Destination Loyalty

[7.6] Elements of Service Quality influencing the tourists to be loyal towards Shaam-E-Sarhad Village Resort in Hodka Village

Table – 7 displays the factors (element of service quality) those are influencing the tourists to recommend this place to the others including their friends and relatives. It is very clear that, whenever the ‘service quality’ closely matches the expectations of the tourists they do not hesitate to recommend or refer the place to the others.

Reasons behind Recommendations & Revisit Intentions	Service Quality
	Accommodation
	Room facilities
	Resort ambience
	Food Quality
	Traditional Architecture
	Hospitality from Resort People
	Tourist Amenities
	Raw, scheduled, great traditional Kutchi Food
	Warm Staffs
	Traditional Kutchi Culture
	Authenticity of products
	Crafts village
	Polite and Helpful Host Community
	Music & way of Life
	Overall Cleanliness
Reasonable Price	
Easy Booking Facility	

Table 7- Elements of Service Quality influencing the tourists to be loyal towards this place

[7.7] Service Gaps

Table 8 highlights few select ‘Service Gap’ issues those have been repetitively mentioned in the tourists’ complaints against the ‘quality of services’ provided at Shaam –E –Sarhad resort in Hodka Village.

Insufficient numbers of pedestal fans / rooms fails to escape the blistering heat during day-time.
Lack of basic amenities often makes tourists bored inside their rooms as this place is quiet and aloof.
Intercom service is not up to the mark.
Room service facility is not impressive.
Lots of complaints against the timing of hot water service and its availability.
Though food quality is good at Shaam – E- Sarhad, but food has limited staff.
Remote location without proper signage. Slightly away from the main road and in the evening we found it very difficult to locate it.
There is no other good restaurant except the Shaam –E-Sarhad in the vicinity. Therefore, every time, tourists come to this village resort they have to take ‘All Meal Package’ that restricts tourists to take food from outside.
Few tourists have found litters inside the campus that makes environment somehow unhygienic.
Housekeeping service should be more flawless.
Few reported against the inconsistency of power supply.
Many a time Foods are prepared well advanced even when tourists have not reached at the restaurant.
Few tourists reported against the ‘stubborn attitude’ of the staffs here as they are very much strict about the timings while a good number of tourists feel that there should be some short of flexibility.
Lack of professionalism and sometime shortage of resort staff that lingers service delivery.
There is a scope for the resort staffs and the villagers to improve their language proficiency (especially Hindi) as a larger number of people come from the north India, where Hindi is most popular language.
Irregularity in conducting the cultural programme at the resort in the evening.

Table 8 – Service Gaps at Shaam –E- Sarhad Village resort at Hodka village, Gujarat, India

[8] Discussion

The researchers feel that there should be more focus on minimizing the service gaps so that the overall ‘Service Quality’ can be more impressive, and flawless. The more the villagers of Hodka and the authority of the village resort Shaam-E-Sarhad will make their guests satisfied, the more tourists’ loyalty towards this rural tourism site will be increased and as a result, the tourism business here will be more sustained that will also benefit the host community as tourism activity diversifies the scope for earning that has a positive impact on the livelihood of the host community people. Therefore, the suggestions from the researchers in the context of Hodka Village with a special reference to its Shaam-E-Sarhad village resort are as follow:

- The intercom services should be improved so that there can be a proper channel of communication.
- There should be proper road signage so that tourists don’t face any difficulty to reach this village resort.

- Their resort should provide basic amenities like TV, sufficient number of pedestal fans at every room so that tourists can enjoy more while spending time inside their rooms.
- Proper sanitation facilities should be there.
- The solar heater can be installed to serve hot water to the tourists 24x7.
- Housekeeping Service should be more flawless.
- To make power supply regular, renewable energy generation sources can be used.
- Local villagers should be encouraged to open more food outlets in this vicinity to offer the tourists the chance to taste a variety of local cuisines, and such practice will benefit the villagers economically as well.
- There should be more variety of food choices for the tourists both in breakfast and dinner at the resort.
- There should be more options for cultural activities so that more tourists can participate in it and even if any day the programme would be cancelled for any reason the resort management should intimate it to their guests in time or have to arrange some alternative provision to get entertained.
- It is very important that staff should be more polite while interacting with clients.
- Skill development programmes for the resort staffs and the villagers can be conducted to enhance their communication skill, language proficiency that can help them to understand what tourists are expecting from them.
- More professionalism is required to entertain and satisfy high value tourists especially the international tourists.
- Rewards, Certificates, Incentives etc. can be offered to the employees to acknowledge their work and it will surely encourage them to do their tasks more efficiently and professionally.

[9] Conclusion

The importance of service quality in rural tourism plays an imperative mechanism towards the employment generation, poverty reduction, sustainable human development, development of rural areas and its environmental regeneration. A better service quality available at any tourism destination can increase the number of ‘more satisfied tourists’ and as we all know, satisfaction quite often encourages the tourists to revisit a place and repurchase tourism products /services , that will ensure a flow of uninterrupted money in the local economy. The local and state government has their responsibilities to promote its select rural sites those are having great tourism potentials and there should also be few monitoring bodies those will collect tourist’s feedbacks and complaints regularly to understand the service gaps at the destination and to follow up the tourists’ ever-changing demands that will make them aware of what sort of improvement is needed for tourism development in terms of attractions, accessibility, accommodation, amenities and activities (5 A’s of tourism development) in a specific rural tourism sites. The authors also suggest the local and/or state government and the local tourism stakeholders to come forward to conduct more and more skill development programmes in rural India to enhance the communication skill of the villagers so that they don’t face any difficulty to communicate with their guests (tourists) and it will encourage them to exchange their ethnic cultures with the tourists coming from distant places. Finally we can say, if service quality at any destination can be improved, more tourists would be

satisfied that can increase tourists' loyalty towards a destination and it will ensure a stabled tourism business that would benefit all tourism stakeholders including the host community.

Bibliography

- [1] Akroush, M. N., Jraisat, L. E., Kurdieh, D. J., AL-Faouri, R. N., & Qatu, L. T. (2016). Tourism service quality and destination loyalty—the mediating role of destination image from international tourists' perspectives. *Tourism Review*, 71(1), 18-44.
- [2] Bauer, H. H., Grether, M., & Leach, M. (2002). Building customer relations over the Internet. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 31(2), 155-163.
- [3] Bitner, M. J., & Hubbert, A. R. (1994). Encounter satisfaction versus overall satisfaction versus quality. *Service quality: New directions in theory and practice*, 34, 72-94.
- [4] Boulding, W., Kalra, A., Staelin, R., & Zeithaml, V. A. (1993). A dynamic process model of service quality: from expectations to behavioral intentions. *Journal of marketing research*, 30(1), 7.
- [5] Buhalis, D. (2000). Marketing the competitive destination of the future. *Tourism management*, 21(1), 97-116.
- [6] Chen, C. F., & Tsai, M. H. (2008). Perceived value, satisfaction, and loyalty of TV travel product shopping: Involvement as a moderator. *Tourism management*, 29(6), 1166-1171.
- [7] Chen, J. S., & Gursoy, D. (2001). An investigation of tourists' destination loyalty and preferences. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 13(2), 79-85.
- [8] Chi, C. G. Q., & Qu, H. (2008). Examining the structural relationships of destination image, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty: An integrated approach. *Tourism management*, 29(4), 624-636.
- [9] Chi, C. G. Q., & Qu, H. (2009). Examining the relationship between tourists' attribute satisfaction and overall satisfaction. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 18(1), 4-25.
- [10] Crompton, J. L. (1995). Economic impact analysis of sports facilities and events: Eleven sources of misapplication. *Journal of sport management*, 9(1), 14-35.
- [11] Demir, Ş. Ş. (2013). The relationship among expectation, perceived quality-value and satisfaction: A study on undergraduate students of tourism Beklenti, algılanan kalite-değer ve memnuniyet ilişkisi: Turizm lisans öğrencileri üzerine bir uygulama. *Journal of Human Sciences*, 10(1), 307-324.
- [12] Faullant, R., Matzler, K., & Füller, J. (2008). The impact of satisfaction and image on loyalty: the case of Alpine ski resorts. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 18(2), 163-178.
- [13] Fen, Y. S. and Meillian, K. (2005). Service quality and customer satisfaction: Antecedents of customer's re-patronage, *Sunway Academic Journal*, (4), 60-73.
- [14] Fyall, A., & Leask, A. (2006). Destination marketing: Future issues—Strategic challenges. *Tourism and hospitality research*, 7(1), 50-63
- [15] Gremler, D. D., & Brown, S. W. (1996). Service loyalty: its nature, importance, and implications. *Advancing service quality: A global perspective*, 5, 171-181.
- [16] Gupta, A., & Chen, I. (1995). Service quality: implications for management development. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 12(7), 28-35.
- [17] Johnston, R., & Silvestro, R. (1990). The determinants of service quality—a customer-based approach. In *The proceedings of the decision science institute Conference, San Diego, CA, November*. Macmillan Indian Ltd.

- [18] Jraisat, L. E., & Sawalha, I. H. (2013). Quality control and supply chain management: a contextual perspective and a case study. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 18(2), 194-207.
- [19] Kasper, H., Helsdingen, V.P. & Gabbott, M. (1999), *Service Marketing Management, A Strategic Perspective*, John Wiley & Sons, West Sussex.
- [20] Kim, A. K., & Brown, G. (2012). Understanding the relationships between perceived travel experiences, overall satisfaction, and destination loyalty. *Anatolia*, 23(3), 328-347.
- [21] Kim, S. H., Holland, S., & Han, H. S. (2013). A structural model for examining how destination image, perceived value, and service quality affect destination loyalty: A case study of Orlando. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 15(4), 313-328.
- [22] Kotler, P. (2003). *Marketing management, 11th ed. Upper Saddle river New Jersey Pearson Education, Inc., 132-133*
- [23] Kozak, M., & Beaman, J. (2006). Relationship between satisfaction and future behavior. *Tourism Analysis*, 11(6), 397-409.
- [24] Kozak, M., & Rimmington, M. (2000). Tourist satisfaction with Mallorca, Spain, as an off-season holiday destination. *Journal of travel research*, 38(3), 260-269.
- [25] Kumar, V., Smart, P. A., Maddern, H., & Maull, R. S. (2008). Alternative perspectives on service quality and customer satisfaction: the role of BPM. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 19(2), 176-187.
- [26] Lee, G. G., & Lin, H. F. (2005). Customer perceptions of e-service quality in online shopping. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 33(2), 161-176.
- [27] Lee, J., Graefe, A. R., & Burns, R. C. (2007). Examining the antecedents of destination loyalty in a forest setting. *Leisure Sciences*, 29(5), 463-481.
- [28] McKercher, B., & Prideaux, B. (2011). Are tourism impacts low on personal environmental agendas?. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 19(3), 325-345.
- [29] Moon, K., Kim, M., Ko, Y., Connaughton, D. and Lee, J. (2011), —The influence of consumer's event quality perception on destination image, *Managing Service Quality*, Vol. 21 No. 3, pp. 287-303.
- [30] Noe, F. P., & Uysal, M. (1997). Evaluation of outdoor recreational settings: A problem of measuring user satisfaction. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 4(4), 223-230.
- [31] Oliver, R. L. (1993). A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Service Satisfaction: Comparative Goals, Different Concepts. *Advances in service marketing and management*, 2, 65-85.
- [32] Oliver, R. L., & DeSarbo, W. S. (1988). Response determinants in satisfaction judgments. *Journal of consumer research*, 14(4), 495-507.
- [33] Oppermann, M. (2000). Tourism destination loyalty. *Journal of travel research*, 39(1), 78-84.
- [34] Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1985). A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research. *The Journal of Marketing*, 41-50.
- [35] Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1988). Servqual: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perc. *Journal of retailing*, 64(1), 12.
- [36] Petrick, J. F., Morais, D. D., & Norman, W. C. (2001). An examination of the determinants of entertainment vacationers' intentions to revisit. *Journal of Travel Research*, 40(1), 41-48.
- [37] Pine, B. J., Peppers, D., & Rogers, M. (1995). *Do you want to keep your customers forever?*. Harvard Business Press.
- [38] Rajesh, R. (2013). Impact of tourist perceptions, destination image and tourist satisfaction on destination loyalty: A conceptual model. *PASOS. Revista de Turismo y Patrimonio Cultural*, 11(3).

- [39] Ramsaran-Fowdar, R. R. (2007). Developing a service quality questionnaire for the hotel industry in Mauritius. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 13(1), 19-27.
- [40] Riduan, S., & Fauzi, A. Darminto. (2015). The effect of tourism service quality, tourist destination image and experience of tourist toward tourist satisfaction, tourism word of mouth, tourist destination preferences, and tourist destination loyalty (a study on foreign tourists in tourist destinations area in Indonesia). *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(2), 95-103.
- [41] Singh, K., Gantait, A., Puri, G., Swamy, A. (2016). Rural Tourism: Need, Scope and Challenges in Indian Context. Hospitality and Tourism: *Challenges, Innovation, Practices and Product Development*. (Ed), Dr. Alok Kumar, Adhyayan Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi
- [42] Sparks, B. A. (2002). *Visitor Satisfaction Survey on the Gold Coast*. Common Ground Publishing.
- [43] Taylor, S. A., & Baker, T. L. (1994). An assessment of the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in the formation of consumers' purchase intentions. *Journal of retailing*, 70(2), 163-178.
- [44] Vinh, N. Q., & Long, N. L. (2013). THE RELATIONSHIP AMONG EXPECTATION, SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY OF INTERNATIONAL VISITOR TO HANOI, VIETNAM. *Journal of global management*, 5(1).
- [45] Walker, D. (1990). *Customer first: A strategy for quality service*. Aldershot: Gower.
- [46] Yang, C. C., Chen, P. S., & Chien, Y. H. (2014). Customer expertise, affective commitment, customer participation, and loyalty in B & B services. *International Journal of Organizational Innovation (Online)*, 6(4), 174.
- [47] Yi, Y. (1990). A critical review of consumer satisfaction. *Review of marketing*, 4(1), 68-123.
- [48] Yoon, Y., & Uysal, M. (2005). An examination of the effects of motivation and satisfaction on destination loyalty: a structural model. *Tourism management*, 26(1), 45-56.
- [49] Žabkar, V., Brenčič, M. M., & Dmitrović, T. (2010). Modelling perceived quality, visitor satisfaction and behavioral intentions at the destination level. *Tourism management*, 31(4), 537-546.

Webliography

- [1] <http://tourism.gov.in/rural-tourism>
- [2] <http://tourism.gov.in/sites/default/files/Rural%20Tourism%20Sites%20and%20their%20USPs.pdf>
- [3] <http://www.pib.nic.in/newsite/erecontent.aspx?relid=32268>
- [4] <http://www.thealternative.in/lifestyle/travel-another-india-visiting-your-roots/>
- [5] http://www.vikalpsangam.org/static/media/uploads/Vikalp%20Sangam%20Case%20Studies/casestudy_shaamesarhad_seema.pdf
- [6] <https://archive.org/details/SustainabilityInTourism-ARuralTourismModel>
- [7] https://www.equitabletourism.org/files/fileDocuments913_uid15.pdf
- [8] www.hodka.in
- [9] www.worldtravelawards.com